

The editor's-in-chief address

Dear Reader!

An attentive reader of UIS must have noticed that the traditional component of the publication content — the so-called Preface — has changed a little bit and has become similar to the classical Foreword. Its sustainable semantic dominant is a brief overview, since the time of the previous issue, of important socially significant events in the field of information, trends, initiatives, which involve journalism and journalists, and which in the current issue of the journal are referred to in separate article.

According to the author of these lines, it is necessary to do this in a scientific professional journalistic publication, first of all, because at the turn of the Ukrainian statehood any glimpses of trends and initiatives in the media environment become relevant. It is crucially important not just to notice, capture, but also to show a convincing motivation for young researchers to study, summarize, and introduce these things to future studies, curriculum or manuals. This will bring real journalistic practice, its standards, principles, lessons and individual work closer to the educational and scientific environment, where personnel for the media industry are formed or hardened.

This issue was being prepared for publication under the conditions of the unprecedented war for the destruction of the Ukrainian nation, which was launched on February 24 by our eternal enemy, russia. Therefore, the content of “journalism and war” inevitably becomes the main thing here.

So, here are several of the most significant phenomena from the hot journalism workshop that need to be understood.

The phenomenon of unified national news deserves the first place. The journalistic community has already named it their native Ukrainian TV and radio miracle. This is an unprecedented case of uniting different forms of ownership (private,

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state, public) and the creative policy of television and radio editorial offices for the main thing — to speak to people in the language of truth; speak in a single Ukrainian voice. Who is in this like-minded team? Public “Ukrainian Radio”, TV channels “Rada”, “Inter”, ICTV, “1+1” and “Ukraine 24”. In a short time, they managed to push out the threatening chronic diseases of Ukrainian journalism into the backyard of history, which everyone knew about but did not have a recipe for to get rid of in time — promoting the interests of oligarchic owners through certain channels, hidden political advertising, low-quality entertainment shows in the Russian wrapper, brazen disregard for the law on the state language, etc. No matter how long such an endeavor lasts, there are already good reasons to talk about a new era in the history of modern Ukrainian journalism.

It is possible to argue about the circle of the “single voice” participants, about the motives of the second package of the National Security and Defense Council regarding putting in order in the national information space. However, it is impossible to continue the games of freedom of speech under martial law. Otherwise a number of oligarchs bag-dependent journalists will continue to interpret these standards one-sidedly.

Journalistic texts’ vocabulary is changing before our eyes. In fact, the entire journalistic corps “in the field” had to learn terms and concepts that are not usually taught in universities. In the beginning, annoying confusion prevailed in terms close in sound, but different in principle, such as: *war — armed aggression — invasion; occupants — invaders — terrorists; combat operations — military operations; bombing — shelling — air raids*, etc. Therefore, a kind of “dictionary of war” published by the Commission on Journalistic Ethics, which emphasizes the responsibility of journalists in the correct choice of vocabulary and professional use of terms, was too timely.

In extreme conditions, a special authority among consumers of various genres’ texts is acquired by those of their creators who have a great ability to find and select facts, to tell about them convincingly and not without charisma. Especially when it comes to live journalism. A vivid example was shown by the now known British-German-Luxembourg reporter Philip Crowther in Ukraine. With his reports from Kyiv, he forced millions of TV viewers in various European countries to watch the events in Kyiv on the eve and in the first days of the Russian aggressor’s invasion with genuine interest. His live broadcasts to Europe took place six times a day, and each time he did so in different languages — English, French, Portuguese, Spanish, German, Luxembourgish. This example is an incentive for our young “pen workers” to learn foreign languages more actively, to boldly expand the Ukrainian information field on Western European or American continents, because a perfect knowledge of one or two, and in the case of our colleague Crowther — six foreign languages — is a convincing sign of higher professionalism. Unfortunately, the realities of our journalism education

are still different: a graduate of the relevant faculty with a university degree can often not boast of perfect knowledge not only of a foreign language, but also of the language of their country.

We have the first experience of national journalism existence under an occupation regime. Thus, for the Velykopysarivska community residents in the Sumy region, their favorite district newspaper Vorskla resumed its activities in the form of a frontline postcard. Neither the printing house nor the post office worked. But the newspaper came to readers. Reduced format, reduced in the number of columns, reproduced on the printer. Volunteers distributed it in the villages and at the front with the time-tested slogan “Read — pass it on to a fellow”. I am convinced that these unusual front-line newspaper issues will eventually become invaluable documents of the day for future chroniclers of this region and Ukraine.

The Ministry of Culture of Ukraine recently pointed out the importance of the “chronicle of modernity” and the role of journalism in this process. They urged all Ukrainians to share their own stories about the war. “Millions of Ukrainians have witnessed russia’s cynical war against Ukraine in the heart of Europe,” the statement said. Share your personal story about the war in our country! This is how the whole world will hear us!”

In this context, the creative exercise of these lines author for the first-year students of the Faculty of Journalism of KNUKIM (KNUC&A), who study the subject “Fundamentals of Journalism” was pretty consistent. Most of them have already written their works on “russian-Ukrainian war: my story”. A selection of the best materials is planned for publication on the pages of the all-Ukrainian weekly “Slovo Prosvity” (“World of Enlightenment”), as well as in the next issue of “Ukrainian Information Space”.

It is worth to note another trend: increasing the role of investigative journalism function. The heroic act is shown, for example, by reporters of the journalistic investigations program “Slidstvo.Info”: thanks to modern technical means, it was possible to identify more than 50 russian servicemen who committed crimes against peaceful Ukrainians during the occupation of certain settlements of Kyiv region. This half a hundred and thousands of other criminals are bound to be punished.

Another aspect of this problem is russia’s crimes against journalists and the media in Ukraine. Their number reached 150 at the end of March, and the number of our colleagues killed in the war — about 20. This mourning list is known to have been opened by the American journalist from “The New York Times” Brent Reno. So, it is necessary to create a Martyrology of those who laid down their lives in the battle on the Ukrainian information front, honestly fulfilling their professional duty.

Finally — about two negative trends.

The first concerns various types of coach-based experts and irresponsible bloggers. Systematically publishing in the open network data not al-

lowed during the war (for example, about the “Neptune” missile plant, the repair of the rashists’ trophy equipment), such “scribblers” become the instigators of point strikes on our infrastructure. And this is not journalism but collaboration. A convincing warning for such people was the appeal of the Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of Ukraine on April 23.

The second trend about the alarming effects of which today should be rung all the bells are journalistic texts’ language illiteracy. Such a complete disregard for one of the fundamental components of professional journalism as editing texts before their publication seems to have not even been in the worst times of the national devastation — the 20s of the twentieth century. Proofreading after texts’ translation from Russian into Ukrainian is stubbornly ignored even by those editions that were still considered the samples of professionalism. Language twists, elementary grammatical negligence, under-reading, underwriting, and all this is an elementary disrespect for the reader. That is what follows this trend.

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of “Ukrainian Information Space”